

ISic0312

Inscribed statue base for Lucius Rubrius Proculus

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Serena Agodi,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 1335

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L (ucio) Rubrio Proculo
3. Iivir (o) quin (quennali)
4. auguri

Apparatus

Translation (en)

To Lucius Rubrius Proculus, quinquennial duumvir, augur

Translation (it)

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491519

EDR 139968

EDCS 21900347

Bibliography

- Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7028 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)
- Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 21
- Libertini, G 1937. Il Castello Ursino e le raccolte artistiche comunali di Catania. At 68
- Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At tav.15
- Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 172 fig.144
- Mole Ventura, C 1996. Catania in eta imperiale. In Gentile, B.(eds.), *Catania Antica. Atti del Convegno della S.I.S.A.C. (Catania 23-24 maggio 1992)*. Pisa. pp. 175-222. At 184, 190

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0312. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335103>